

The Becoming of the Society: Perspectives from Aristotle and J. J. Rousseau

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ABSTRACT: In the contemporary parlance, in our references to the social life, to our social competences or to our social priorities, it is important to realize that the society as we know it today is the result of many years of interactions, regardless if such interactions were peaceful or violent. The society is still changing and becoming something else every day. We are responsible for that, and we know it. Nevertheless, we are unable to curtail change because social movement is infinite. Therefore, this paper surveys several basic perspectives offered by the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle, and by the French philosopher, J. J. Rousseau.

KEY WORDS: society, culture, law, equality, natural, social, state, liberty, savage, social structure, civic life.

(1) What Does Society Mean?

The concept of society is a very intense disputed topic in the entire world, between scientists or non scientists, between common or specialists, in each domain, in all activity sectors, in a more or less scientific way. Anyhow, each debate is concentrated around the idea that society is an integral piece of each human being. Its importance is justified by the opinion that it is the most important part of our life. What is a person without society? What does he/she believe he/she can have without it? What is good

and what is wrong in his life? All these questions can lead us to the deepest level of understanding the meaning of a society.

The identity of a person is given by the place, the space, the culture and the medium that he/she inherited and where he/she develops each day. The sum of these types of factors gives birth to the society in a very general meaning. Society is our home, society is our space and our time and everyone's reason to be.

It's impossible to define society without talking about the concept of culture. Even if in our daily conversations, when we talk about culture, we refer mostly to a higher level of education, culture is rather the way a group of people are living. This includes the way they dress, the culinary tastes, the customs, the traditions and so on. Without culture we couldn't be humans and we couldn't have our own identity which is, after all, the group identity.

But how can we define society? There are a few main characteristics that we refer to when we try to determine the specificity of society.

First of all there is a specific delimited space, the territory, the natural habitat that houses the people. It represents the nucleus of the social interactions, the physical or the material aspect of a group.

Secondly, we can refer to the ability of keeping an intense and constant interaction between its members, interaction sustained by something that all the people have in common, such as similar values. The French sociologist Emilé Durkheim was saying that the most important characteristic of society is the presence of the *collective conscience* (Durkheim 2002). This can chase away selfishness and let the people be a homogeneous group. With the constant interaction of members arises stability. Stability guarantees the continuous presence of a collective behavior which promotes continuous acceptance. Because of this, the number of members is growing very fast and the effect is the emergence of the social structure.

The Romanian sociologists Cătălin Zamfir and Lazăr Vlăsceanu define the social structure as "the ensemble of the relationships which are quite stable and which characterize the social system of a society made of communities, collectivities, classes, categories and social groups that have their own existence at a time" (Org.Ro) (Zamfir, Vlăsceanu 1993). The social structure includes the relations

between different type of human cohabitation and from human activity inside the society. From this point of view, the society can be divided into two categories: the holistic society where the social has the precedence over the individual, and the individualistic society, where the individual precedes the social. Most of the contemporary societies are built like individualistic societies.

Thirdly, society should be able to have the autonomy to function by its own rules. Here are included the institutions, organizations, the rules and the standards created inside the society. The most important thing is that it has self control and its autonomy is based on the lack of exterior constraints.

Nevertheless, society should have a great ability to integrate the new members because the dynamic and the mobility of the population is continuously changing and that's why it's important to be prepared for what is new, with new rules and new institutions if necessary. There are two assumptions referring to the appearance of society. The first one starts from the idea that through their nature, people are social beings and they have a social instinct which leads them towards the others, thus creating the cooperation with those of their kind.

According to the second hypothesis, the people don't have a social instinct because, in nature, far away from the social conventions, they have absolute freedom. Anyway, because at some time they couldn't manage their life and the conflicts, they were forced to adopt a contract and to let themselves guided by rules. This was the main reason for which the people left their natural way of life and became members of a society.

Anyway, the main idea is that society appears as a result of its members' interaction, as a system built on some specific rules, on very particular standards and it is continuously concerned about conservation.

(2) Aristotle and the civic life

Aristotle is well known by its remarkable expression "the human is a social animal" and this remark seemed to explain in a simple way

the fundamentals of any anthropology. He starts from the idea that no person can live alone, isolated, far away from the others. We can live only together, in pairs and communities to fulfill our instinctive calling: to practice the well and to share it with the others.

The first community is the family. The man and the woman look for each other led by a natural instinct to leave behind a descendant, an inheritor. Each of those two spouses has specific attributions, one of them has to lead and the other one has to be led. "Those who can foresee with their mind should be in a natural way the masters and the leaders and those who can realize with their bodies what is foreseen, they should be the obedient in a natural way." (Aristotle 2001, 35) Also, few families compose the village, more villages constitute a colony and more colonies give birth to the city. And this is the way society is formed. The society is a beneficial institution which existed before the humans and that's why it is considered like a pole of attraction for all the people. The society is the salvation of the human race.

According to Aristotle, each society should be characterized by unity, but we are not talking about the Socratic unity where everybody is equal with his/her fellows. We are talking about the *proportional unity*. This new concept refers especially to the differences between people and, most of all it refers to the ethnic differences. In his opinion, the number of different ethnic people should be the same.

Another topic that refers to society is the idea of using collectively all the things, including women and children. He disagrees with the idea of common usage of the goods. If something belongs to someone, then it doesn't belong to anyone because no one takes the responsibility of the personal property over that thing and in this case no one would take care of it.

Besides that, a society which doesn't have a private property is an unhappy one. The people want to feel that they have something of their own, something that they can count, change, sell or give as inheritance. In this case we have to talk about equality. But this new concept of equality is not an abstract one or a theoretical one. Aristotle considered that the equality should be made in fortune and in education. Each person should have the right to have enough

money, or he/she should be rich if he deserves it and works for that. It's almost the same about education. A person, who has the necessary abilities and wants to get an appropriate education, should get it more than another one who is not that gifted with such abilities.

The identity of a city¹ is given by the persistence of the same nation not of its walls. The people have a constitution that they respect and this is enough to protect them. Besides that, each person has a specific virtue which is useful for respecting the constitution. Each person has its own virtue correlated with his/her activity. For example, the leader is educated in a certain way; the common citizen is educated in another way. Each of these two people has an own virtue but their virtues have nothing in common. The leader has the virtue to lead well, while the common citizen has the virtue to be obedient. Anyway, Aristotle is talking about that person who is educated to lead right and who is following the right constitution. He makes the difference between the right constitutions and the deviant constitutions. Those who are right are the monarchy, the aristocracy and the constitutional system. The deviant constitutions would be the tyranny, democracy and the oligarchy.

Other important questions are: who should be the leader for the good of the city? Should it be a rich person or a poor one? Should it be one leader or should there be many of them? The error that appears in those questions, says Aristotle, is the fact that the power is given to humans. The human beings are weak and are tempted to control the others and not to lead them. That is why the power should be in the hands of the law. Before making a law, the legislator should search some things: the constitution that is valid in an absolute way, the best constitution of those who exist, the existent constitution, the constitution that is applicable to a certain society, the differences between constitutions. If he takes into account these aspects, he can formulate right and useful laws for all the citizens.

Aristotle thinks that the most important thing in any constitution or in any city is the *mediation*² which is the middle way between extremes. And this idea is available also in what concerns the goods or the spiritual things. "And the happy life, even if it is made of joys or virtues or both, is due to those who have a good balance between excess of character and intelligence, but who keeps

a measure over the exterior goods, rather than to those who have those goods but they lack the others.” (Aristotle 2001, 373)

In conclusion, Aristotle sees the society like a very strict organization of the people where each member knows what is his/her duty is and which are his/her virtues. So, each person uses his/her own virtue and is doing what he/she knows best and this is the reason why everything is going well. They are organized like a holistic community whose main principle is keeping the middle way in everything and this seems to bring them happiness.

(3) J. J. Rousseau and the Natural Status

If Aristotle is talking about society comparing it with a life boat for humans, J. J. Rousseau is not that delighted about this. He thinks that the society is the result of the evolution process but not in a beneficial way. According to Rousseau, the society is responsible for perverting the human soul and making them very unhappy.

He describes the savage people, absolutely free and happy, living like animals and behaving like it. “I see an animal less powerful and less agile than the others but anyway better organized than all the animals. I see it quenching its hunger under an oak and its thirst in the first met stream, finding a place to sleep under the tree that feeds it—so there you have its necessities satisfied.” (Rousseau 2001, 29, 30)

The savage imitates animals’ gestures and he learns from them how to hunt, how to fight, how to survive. That’s why the animals consider him one of their kind and, more than that, some of them are afraid of him and don’t fight with him. The savage has a robust body, strong and tough to diseases and accustomed to unfavorable circumstances. He isn’t afraid of anything except the childhood, the old age and the disease. All these are the signs of weakness and he doesn’t like to be weak. His only concern is his own conservation. This is why he can be untroubled and happy.

But, even so, his great quality which became his biggest disadvantage is his ability to improve his self every day. After all, this is also the main difference between him and other animals.

Because of this, the humans evolved that much and became how we know them today. “What else could deprave him that much if not the changing that appeared in his structure, the progresses that he had made and the knowledge that he had acquired? We can admire the society as much as we like—it won’t be less true that it pushes the people to hate each other when they have common interests, to offer apparent favors to each other, but in fact to cause each other all the bad that we can imagine.” (Rousseau 2001, 98)

This description of social human reveals the idea that the savage didn’t have virtues or vices. He had only love and care for his own person, while the social human has *love of self* which is equal to selfishness. And Rousseau continues the idea of differences between those types of love like that: “The humans wouldn’t be anything else but some monsters if nature wouldn’t give them the compassion sustained by reason . . . to want for someone to be unhurt is not the same thing like to want for him to be happy?” (Rousseau 2001, 49)

As I was saying before, the society is the result of human evolution. The first step in their evolution is the language. At the beginning, the savage was using some gestures but, in time, he started to make some noises and after a while he could say words and even sentences. This was a crucial point in human’s evolution.

After that, the human realized that he is superior to the other animals and this made him proud and determined him to use his mental abilities, rather than his physical skills. He observed that it is easier to hunt like that and to get his food this way. After a while he realized that it is better to live in common with the others because they can protect each other and they are stronger like that. This way the feeling of marital life and the kindness arose in his soul. With time, families had more and more interactions; they started to share the lands and this way private property appeared. “The first man who enclosed a land daring to say ‘this is mine’ and succeeded to find enough naive people to believe him, that was the true founder of the civil society.” (Rousseau 2001, 58) So this is the way that the civil society was born.

So far nothing seems to be wrong with society. In fact, we could say it is even better than before. But, along with the intellectual development of the human, the physical power became weaker and

weaker each day. Also, because of the new way of living, this new man learned how to cook and how to work the land, to cultivate plants and use them in the kitchen. It didn't take long until his body started to feel the weaknesses and also the diseases. He needed to be cured and to recover. Now he needs the others more than any other time. He created his dependence of them.

On the other hand, some of the new people became rich and started to enslave the others. Because life was chaotic and most of the people couldn't be able to protect themselves they were forced to make laws. But the law didn't help them so much because most of the legislators made abusive laws thus the tyranny appeared. So this is the way that the savage man became a slave for those of his own kind.

If we compare the savage and the social human, we can say that the savage is living within his self, peaceful and happy, while the social man lives outside him through the others, working hard and struggling every day, dependant of others' opinions and beliefs. This is the result of his progress, that "happy" life he was dreaming of. Sometimes, says Rousseau, I have the impression that reason is a malefic mood: "I almost dare to say that the thinking condition is an unnatural one and the man who thinks is a degenerated animal." (Rousseau 2001, 33)

According to Rousseau, the natural status was the best one for the people, the normal way of life for mankind. But, even so, the progress was unavoidable because, as Rousseau is forced to admit, the most important characteristic of the human being is his capacity to improve his self every day. So, as a sad but true conclusion, Rousseau seems to end his pleading with these words: "the human was born free but he is always in chains." (Rousseau 2003, 6)

Even if we refer to the Aristotle's assumption about society, or to Rousseau's pleading for natural life, one thing seems to be obvious: society is created by its members' interaction and evolution, by their good and bad decisions, by their truth and by their untruth, by their efforts and errors. The society is the sum of all positive and negative things that the human being can produce. Or, in Terentiu's words, we could say, "I am a human being and thus nothing human is strange for me."

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NOTES

¹ The original name of the *city* in Aristotle's writings is *fortress* and every time he refers to what we call *city* today, he means *fortress*.

² The most appropriate word would be *mediaty*.